

MS access invoicing

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To fully understand the value of relational database you need to create a detailed system. In this practical you will setup an invoicing system for a computer mail order company, PC Direct, which sells computer peripherals through the mail. The invoice system will then be completed in the following steps. There are three main sections to the system, customers, products and the sales invoice.

In the creation of any database system you should do some careful planning. In general there are four steps that should undertake.

Steps

- 1:** Decide how many tables you think you might need.
- 2:** Decide how the tables will be related to one another.
- 3:** List the fields in each table trying to avoid having the same field in more than one table. Decide which fields will be the PRIMARY KEY and FOREIGN KEY fields to link the tables.
- 4:** Decide what forms and/or reports (or printouts) are required

Problems

There is a problem with the link between the INVOICE and the PRODUCTS tables.

The one invoice can contain many products and the one product can be included in many invoices. A relational database cannot cater for a MANY TO MANY relationship as you cannot set multiple PRIMARY or FOREIGN KEY fields in the one relationship.

A further problem exists, one invoice might contain a sale of 5 of a particular item, and the next invoice might contain a sale of 2 of the same item. The company needs a way of adding these sales so that it knows how many items it has sold. So this initial TABLE RELATIONSHIP will need modification.

Solutions

The easiest solution to these problems is to add a table between INVOICE and PRODUCTS. This table can store every item sold by the company as a single record allowing the company to keep track of every item sold. The new table can also provide data to the INVOICE table.